

PERIODONTAL DISEASES IN ELDERLY AND GERIATRIC INDIVIDUALS**Gurbanov R.Y.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, assistant
Department of Therapeutic Dentistry***Rustamov E.A.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant***Gurskaya N.A.***Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant**Department of Orthopedic Dentistry**Azerbaijan Medical University**Baku, Azerbaijan***ABSTRACT**

The study is motivated by the high prevalence of periodontal diseases among elderly and geriatric individuals. Periodontal diseases are the most common cause of tooth loss, which not only leads to changes in dental health but also contributes to a decline in the quality of life for this population group.

Keywords: elderly and geriatric individuals, dental diseases, generalized periodontitis.

Periodontal diseases are among the most pressing issues in dentistry and are a leading cause of early tooth loss, significantly affecting the quality of life, particularly among elderly individuals [12]. The highest incidence of periodontal diseases occurs between the ages of 40 and 45, and their prevalence among elderly individuals, according to many researchers, is 100% [9]. Maintaining overall health and oral health, as well as successful treatment of periodontal diseases, is only possible when the patient consistently follows proper oral hygiene procedures. The success of virtually every aspect of clinical dentistry—ranging from primary prevention (when there are no diseases) to maintaining the results of even the most complex treatments—depends on the level of individual oral hygiene, prolonging the remission period of periodontal diseases. For patients in older age groups, maintaining oral hygiene is the simplest, most reliable, and, most importantly, the most accessible way to extend the remission period. It is essential that the patient is informed, educated, and motivated [8, 10]. However, educating geriatric patients on oral hygiene and motivating them is a challenging task. Elderly individuals have developed long-standing habits and stereotypes regarding oral care. As a result, it is difficult for them to revise and change their usual approach to oral hygiene to align with the changing state of the dentition. With age, there are changes in dental status, a decrease in the number of natural teeth, and the appearance of prosthetic constructions [3]. Secondary partial edentulism, the absence of antagonistic teeth, leads to impaired self-cleaning of the teeth, inadequate redistribution of chewing forces, and, consequently, the development of secondary traumatic occlusion. In the absence of a large number of teeth, the number of teeth requiring individual hygienic care is also reduced. However, this does not mean that oral hygiene procedures can be ignored. The decrease in saliva production, its increased viscosity due to age-related factors or medication use, also contributes to the formation and accumulation of soft dental plaque [4]. Among the various factors influencing the prevalence of periodontal diseases and determining their development and course, age-related characteristics remain the least

studied. It has been shown that periodontal diseases are the most common cause of tooth loss among elderly (55–74 years) and senile (75–89 years) individuals, leading not only to changes in dental health but also to a deterioration in the quality of life for this population group [6, 7, 12, 14]. The problem of treating periodontal diseases in this category of patients is complicated by the depth of pathological changes in the periodontal tissues, changes in dental status, as well as the overall medical health condition (presence of somatic and systemic diseases), social, and economic factors [9, 15]. Therefore, the development of methods for the comprehensive treatment of periodontal diseases and the restoration of their function in elderly and senile individuals is a relevant issue in clinical dentistry and has significant practical importance. In connection with this, the aim of this study was to justify a comprehensive approach in choosing methods for the treatment of periodontal tissue diseases in elderly and senile individuals by studying the risk factors involved.

Materials and Methods of Research.

We observed 67 elderly and senile patients who consented to undergo examination and treatment. The patients were divided into two groups: the first group included 45 patients aged 55–74 years, with an average age of 65.2 ± 0.8 years. The second group consisted of 22 patients aged 75–89 years, with an average age of 78.4 ± 0.5 years.

Diagnosis of periodontal disease was conducted using the classification of periodontal diseases by N.F. Danilevsky [5]. The condition of periodontal tissues was assessed using periodontal probes and indices, oral hygiene was evaluated using the Green-Vermilion hygiene index, the condition of the tooth hard tissues was determined using the CPITN index, and the need for treatment was evaluated according to the CPI index.

The overall somatic status was studied through patient questionnaires and medical records. Statistical processing of the research results was performed using the Student's t-test. A questionnaire was conducted with the patients, focusing on the nature of the previous treatments, the presence of comorbid conditions, harm-

ful habits, dietary patterns, hygiene procedures performed in the oral cavity, the use of specific hygiene products, and the duration of their use. The collected data were recorded in the examination chart. Statistical analysis of the results was performed using the Student's t-test.

Results and Discussion

The prevalence of dental caries in elderly individuals was found to be 100%. The CPITN index in Group I was 19.4 ± 0.28 , and in Group II, it was 21.8 ± 0.40 . Analysis of the components of the CPITN index in the examined patients revealed a predominance of the "U" (extracted) indicator. The "U" indicator was 11.01 ± 0.12 and 12.2 ± 0.14 , respectively, which accounted for 39.32% and 43.89%.

The prevalence of periodontal diseases in elderly and senile patients was 100%. Generalized periodontitis was diagnosed in 75.56% of elderly patients and in 77.27% of senile patients. When analyzing the structure of periodontal diseases, a trend toward a decrease in the initial forms of the disease was observed. A characteristic feature for patients in this age category is the increase in the number of individuals with pronounced manifestations of destructive changes in periodontal tissues, which leads to a prolonged course of the inflammatory process. This is compounded by the lack of preventive examinations, timely diagnosis, and comprehensive treatment.

This is confirmed by the fact that no patients in either age group had a diagnosis established at an early stage. The majority of patients had a disease duration of 15 to 20 years.

Analysis of the CPITN index structure revealed its high prevalence and intensity. A characteristic feature for gerontological patients was the high values of the index due to extracted teeth (U). The number of preserved teeth decreases with age, from 14.61 ± 0.8 in elderly patients to 8.4 ± 0.5 in senile patients. These data are approximately twice as low as the number of preserved teeth recommended by the WHO for this age group [13].

The predominance of extracted teeth indicates a low level of dental care, the lack of timely treatment, and, as a result, poor quality of life. The level of dental care for the population, according to the USP (Leus, 1997), is considered "insufficient" at 36.3%. According to the CPI index, a high frequency (from 52.27% to 75.94%) of excluded sextants was found. The high prevalence of CPI scores "3" and "4" indicates irreversible processes in the periodontal tissues.

Due to the disruption of the integrity of the dental arch, occlusal overload zones form in the periodontal system of the patients, leading to accelerated resorption processes in the alveolar bone. The loss of teeth and the lack of restored occlusion are associated with periodontal overload, pathological tooth mobility, and the development of blockages when teeth shift. Additionally, the quality of food changes, as patients switch to softer foods.

As a result, oral hygiene deteriorates, and masticatory load on the periodontium is reduced. The presence of prosthetic structures, coupled with low motivation among patients for maintaining proper oral hygiene,

contributes to the development and maintenance of inflammation in the periodontal tissues. Regular hygiene procedures (twice a day) are carried out by only 28% of elderly patients and 15% of senile patients. It was found that 18% of elderly individuals do not clean their teeth or removable dentures at all, and 14% do so no more than once every few days. Motivation for performing oral hygiene procedures in the majority of patients from these age groups is absent. The state of care for prosthetic structures is considered to be moderately contaminated.

It is well known that dental plaque creates a favorable environment for the development of pathogenic flora, leading to inflammation in the periodontium. This also contributes to a shift in pH toward acidity, which is accompanied by demineralization of the tooth's hard tissues, the formation of dental calculus, and the creation of periodontal pockets.

The simplified hygiene index (OHI-S) for the examined patients was 4.05 ± 0.23 points in group I and 4.24 ± 0.22 points in group II (Table 1). Motivation among patients for undergoing treatment in these age groups was low. Only 12 patients (26.66%) in the first group and 3 patients (13.64%) in the second group periodically underwent local anti-inflammatory therapy and removed dental deposits.

In this group of patients, root caries (68%), pathological abrasion of tooth hard tissues (51%), wedge-shaped defects (43%), and increased tooth sensitivity to various stimuli (36%) were also found. Pathological tooth mobility of II–III degree was observed in 62%, and significant gingival recession in 44%. Most of the patients had digestive system diseases (84.8%), cardiovascular diseases (58.8%), musculoskeletal disorders (49.2%), and respiratory system diseases (33.6%).

Thus, the factors contributing to the progression of periodontal diseases in this group of individuals are as follows:

- **Diseases of organs and systems** – 83.7%;
- **Socio-economic reasons** – 76.3%;
- **Bad habits (smoking, alcohol consumption, and their prolonged effects on the body)** – 53.1%;
- **Lack of awareness about hygiene products** – 48.3%;
- **Fear of dental procedures and negative reviews from acquaintances** – 46.3%;
- **Dietary habits (limitations in food choices, consumption of soft and monotonous food)** – 45.4%;
- **Duration of treatment and the need for repeated visits** – 35.2%;
- **Presence of dental prostheses, especially removable ones, and poor care for them** – 26.9%.

These age-related disorders of the dentoalveolar system significantly reduce the quality of life for elderly individuals. Consequently, elderly people require all types of dental care—therapeutic, surgical, prosthetic, and periodontal.

However, among all types of dental procedures, tooth extraction is the most common. The results of the study indicate a low level of motivation among elderly individuals to maintain their oral health. This can be attributed to several factors:

- **Inability to visit a dentist independently** due to mobility issues or chronic illnesses;
- **Limited access to care** at local clinics, with some dental services being unavailable or inaccessible (financially) for this population;
- **Difficulties associated with physical weakness** when it comes to personal care, resulting in poor oral hygiene;
- **Psychological changes in older age**, such as mood swings, irritability, and a need for increased attention, which require specific skills from the dentist when working with geriatric patients;
- **Lack of additional healthcare programs** providing dental care for the elderly population at the public healthcare level.

These factors contribute to the challenge of ensuring proper oral care and treatment for older individuals.

When developing and justifying treatment and preventive measures for elderly and senile patients, it is necessary to follow modern methodological approaches in selecting comprehensive therapy for patients diagnosed with caries and generalized periodontitis. In addition, age-related, social, and psychological characteristics of patients in these age groups must be taken into account.

Important criteria when choosing treatment methods and means include the etiological and pathogenetic focus of the therapeutic agents, their accessibility, and the improvement of the quality of life for elderly patients.

Basic treatment for elderly patients should be based on motivating the patients to undergo treatment, educating them on proper individual oral hygiene, as well as performing professional hygiene, treating caries and its complications, and providing supportive treatment within the framework of dynamic dispensary observation.

Conclusion

The issue of treating patients with generalized periodontitis in elderly and senile age is particularly relevant, as early tooth extraction due to this disease leads to dysfunction of the masticatory apparatus and a decrease in the quality of life for elderly patients.

When creating a comprehensive set of therapeutic and preventive measures for elderly and senile patients, it is important to consider the need for sanitation of preserved teeth due to the high frequency of caries and its complications, the low level of individual oral hygiene, and the lack of motivation for regular hygiene practices.

The effectiveness of comprehensive therapy for generalized periodontitis largely depends on including rational prosthetics in the treatment plan and restoring lost functional occlusal relationships between the dental arches.

Considering the persistent chronicity and prolonged course of destructive processes in the periodontal tissues, their low reparative potential, and the high general somatic morbidity, when selecting means for local treatment, preference should be given to plant-based hygiene products, which help reduce the drug load on the body, avoid resistance to medications, and improve treatment outcomes.

To eliminate the adverse consequences of the disease and prolong the remission period, prevention, early treatment, constant monitoring of the disease progression, and prolonged supportive therapy through dispensary supervision are necessary.

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